

Alkali Metal Complexes. Neutral Complexes of Alkali Metals with 2-Hydroxy-3-Naphthoic Acid, α -Picolinic Acid and 2-Nitroso-1-Naphthol

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Compounds of the general formula ML_nHL (where M = an alkali metal and HL = 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, α -picolinic acid or 2-nitroso-1-naphthol) have been obtained by reaction between HL and MOH in absolute ethanol.

The isolation of adducts in the solid state appeared to be favoured by increase in radius (or decrease in ionisation potential) of the metal and high pK value of the ligand.

A PART from the early work of Sidgwick and Brewer¹⁻³ and Porter⁴, Nyholm and co-workers have lately prepared a number of neutral complexes of the type ML_nHL with various bidentate ligands^{5,6}.

We have investigated the behaviour of the alkali metals with some potential ligands containing the 'hard atoms' nitrogen and oxygen and have found that for molecules HL [where HL = 2-nitroso-1-naphthol (2N1N), α -picolinic acid (PicA) and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2H3NA)] each having two replaceable hydrogen atoms and also having two donor atoms, suitably placed to form a 5- or 6-membered chelate ring with metal, complexes of the general formula ML_nHL ($n = 1$ or 2) were obtained.

Experimental

Compounds with 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid: A mixture of Rb- or CsOH and 2H3NA in absolute ethanol (ratio 1 : 3) were warmed on a steam bath for an hour and then allowed to cool; the *pale brown* compounds obtained were washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80°. No adduct separated for Li, Na and K.

Compounds with Picolinic acid: A mixture of K-, Rb- or CsOH and picolinic acid in absolute ethanol (ratio 1 : 2 with slight excess of picolinic acid) were refluxed in a steam bath for half an hour. After filtration, the solution was concentrated and then cooled. After hours the *white needles* which were formed were filtered off and dried as above. No adducts separated for Li and Na.

Compounds with 2-nitroso-1-naphthol

Lithium: 2N1N was added to a saturated solution of $LiOH \cdot H_2O$ in absolute ethanol and stirred on a steam bath for half an hour. After filtration the

deep brown solution was concentrated on a steam bath and then cooled in a refrigerator. *Reddish brown* crystals were formed after 24 hr. These were filtered and dried as mentioned above.

Sodium: To an ethanol solution of 2N1N was added NaOH pellets (ratio 1 : 1). The solution was warmed over steam bath for 40 min. After filtration the deep brown solution was concentrated and cooled. The *deep brown* salt obtained after several hours, was suspended in ethanol and excess of 2N1N (ratio 1 : 2) was added and refluxed for an hour and then cooled in a refrigerator. *Reddish brown* powder separated after 24 hr. Potassium and rubidium complexes were synthesised in the same manner as sodium.

Caesium: 2N1N with ethanolic CsOH (ratio 1 : 1) formed greenish brown solution on warming. On cooling the salt, *bottle green needles*, were obtained. This salt with excess of 2N1N (1 : 2) when warmed in absolute ethanol formed brown solution which on rapid cooling yielded *yellowish brown* crystals. If these yellowish brown crystals were refluxed in abs. ethanol with excess of the ligand (1 : 4) or if CsOH in ethanol was warmed with excess of 2N1N (1 : 6) for 1 hr and then cooled slowly in a refrigerator, *deep brown* crystals were obtained after 24 hr.

Results and Discussion

The complexes of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, α -picolinic acid and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol with alkali metals are light brown, white and deep brown in colour respectively. All the complexes are stable when stored under dry condition, e.g., in a desiccator. The compounds showed no change in stoichiometry or physical properties even after one year. If the compounds were exposed to moisture, hydrolysis of the complex to the free ligand and metal salt appeared

to take place. The complexes are soluble in polar solvents such as acetone and absolute ethanol with dissociation but a few complexes are sparingly soluble in non-polar solvents like chloroform and toluene. The colour, transition temperatures ($t^{\circ}\text{C}$) and analytical results are given in Table 1.

system varies with the alkali metals; and is lowest for $M = \text{Cs}$ and highest for $M = \text{Li}$.

Infra-red spectra: Measurements were made in Nujol mulls for all the complexes, salts and ligands between 4000-650 cm^{-1} . The bands occurring in

Compound	Colour	Transition ($t^{\circ}\text{C}$) temperatures	Found%				Calculated%				
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M	
Picolinic acid (PicA)	White	135 m	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
KPicA.PicA	White	155 t	49.68	3.20	9.72	9.75	50.70	3.17	9.85	10.21	—
RbPicA.PicA	White	142 t	46.78	2.75	8.37	24.60	46.66	2.72	8.48	25.75	—
CsPicA.PicA	White	140 t	39.00	2.40	7.35	33.98	38.19	2.38	7.42	35.01	—
2-Hydroxy-3-Naphthoic Acid (2H3NA)	Pale yellow	220 m	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Rb2H3NA.2H3NA	Pale brown	229 t	56.93	3.18	—	18.52	57.39	3.26	—	18.47	—
Cs2H3NA.2H3NA	Pale brown	224 t	51.95	3.02	—	25.48	52.07	2.95	—	26.03	—
2-Nitroso-1-Naphthol (2N1N)	Yellowish green	158-60 m	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Li2N1N.2N1N	Reddish brown	170 t	67.84	3.75	7.24	—	68.18	3.69	7.95	—	—
Na2N1N.2N1N	Reddish brown	200 t	65.85	3.60	7.49	6.20	65.21	3.53	7.61	6.25	—
K2N1N.2N1N	Yellowish brown	170 t	61.88	3.60	6.80	9.70	62.50	3.40	7.30	10.20	—
Rb2N1N.2N1N	Reddish brown	175 t	54.98	3.10	6.30	20.0	55.70	3.00	6.50	19.99	—
Cs2N1N.2N1N	Yellowish brown	180 t	50.60	2.80	5.85	25.90	50.20	2.70	5.90	27.40	—
Cs2N1N(2N1N) ₂	Deep brown	165 t	54.59	3.21	6.25	20.52	54.38	3.07	6.46	20.30	—

TABLE 2
THE NUMBER OF ALKALI METAL COMPLEXES FORMED WITH DIFFERENT LIGANDS

pK Ligands	Compounds									
	SalH	8HQ	INAP	1N2N	2N1N	ONP	Anc	PicA	2H3NA	2,4-DNP
9.58	9.51	8.5	7.7	7.48	7.17	6.97	5.86	4.5	3.86	—
Li 1:2	Li 1:2	X	X	Li 1:2	X	X	X	X	X	X
Na 1:2	Na 1:2	Na 1:2	X	Na 1:2	X	X	X	X	X	X
K 1:2 1:3	K 1:2	K 1:2	K 1:2	K 1:2	K 1:3	K 1:2	K 1:2	X	X	X
Rb 1:2 1:3	Rb 1:3	Rb 1:2	Rb 1:2	Rb 1:3	Rb 1:3	Rb 1:2	Rb 1:2	Rb 1:2	Rb 1:2	X
Cs 1:2 1:3	Cs 1:3	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:2 1:3	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:2	Cs 1:3

On the basis of the evidence below, we conclude that the solid adducts are definite compounds and not mixtures. The transition temperatures of the complexes were higher than the melting points of the corresponding ligands, as is apparent from Table 1.

Physical mixtures of the salts of 2N1N and ligand 2N1N (mole ratio 1:1) melt at 155°, 152°, 152°, 154° and 154° for metals Li, Na, K, Rb and Cs respectively (cf. m.p. for 2N1N = 158°-60°). After transformation a solid remains (presumably through the loss of the extra ligands), which melts at the same temperature as M 2N1N. It is assumed that the transformation consists of breaking the adduct forming bonds at a temperature, which in the given

the regions 3500-3000 cm^{-1} and 1700-1500 cm^{-1} only are listed in Table 3.

The presence of the second extra molecule to the neutral salt may be considered to take place in these two possible ways:

(1) H-bonded structure not involving any additional co-ordinating, over and above that which occurs in the neutral salt, i.e., type A and B acid salts.⁷

(2) H-bonded structure involving co-ordination.

In case of picolinic acid complexes, only band above 3000 cm^{-1} will be due to O-H stretch. Absence of this band from its original position, will be either due to co-ordination or through hydrogen

TABLE 3—INFRA-RED ABSORPTION BANDS IN THE REGIONS 3500–3000 AND 1700–1500 cm^{-1} FOR LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES (MEASURED IN cm^{-1})

2-Nitroso-1-naphthol (2N1N)	3400	3240	1654	1598m	1580	1534
Li2N1N.2N1N			1628	1605	1578	
Na2N1N			1620	1610	1582	1550
Na2N1N.2N1N			1622	1612	1584	1550
K2N1N			1616	1605sh	1574	1554sh
K2N1N.2N1N			1663	1618	1590,	1548
					1580sh	
Rb2N1N			1615	1605sh	1574,	1595
					1555sh	
Rb2N1N.2N1N			1635	1604	1588	1558
Cs2N1N			1612	1604	1590sh	1555,
						1544
Cs2N1N.2N1N			1645	1608	1590	1550
Cs2N1N.(2N1N) ₂			1645sh	1608	1588	1550br
			1640			
Picolinic acid (PicA)	3400br		1650	1600	1580	1520
K(PicA) ₂	3100	1700	1650br	1600	1580,	1520br
					1560	
Rb(PicA) ₂		3055	1720	1630	1600	1580
Cs(PicA) ₂	3380br			1650	1630,	1580
					1605	1560
2-Hydroxy-3-Naphthoic Acid (2H3NA)	3265	1680sh	1660	1620	1590	1500
Rb(2H3HNA) ₂		1670	1650sh	1620	1575	1500
Cs(2H3NA) ₂		1660sh	1640	1605	1560	1500

(anomalous spectra between 1300–700 cm^{-1} .)

bonding. As the shift is of the order of $\sim 350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, this change only due to co-ordination is most improbable; the other factor may be the hydrogen bonding. Moreover, in our previous papers^{5,6}, we have also observed similar shift.

The 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid complexes exhibit a broad absorption between 1300 cm^{-1} and 700 cm^{-1} . This anomalous spectra and absence of any bands above 3000 cm^{-1} would suggest a type A acid salt structure for these compounds.

Neither the broad absorption nor the O–H stretch above 3000 cm^{-1} are observed in 2N1N complexes. The sharp band at 1654 cm^{-1} , has been found to be metal sensitive, both in the salt, as well as, in the complexes. This absorption, shifts considerably to lower frequency ($30\text{--}40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the salts, and to lesser extent ($10\text{--}25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. That these complexes are not physical mixtures of the acid salts and the ligand molecule, are evident not only by the absence of the O–H stretching frequency of the ligand, but also by the fact that spectra of the salts change considerably on the addition of the second molecule, which again in turn is not superimposable with that of the free ligand. Caesium formed two complexes with 2N1N, and the spectra clearly showed the difference between the two (Table 3).

By the study of the pK value of 2H3NA and PicA, we have found that characteristic of these ligands accord well with the observation of Nyholm and Banerjee⁷, that "Isolation of adducts in the solid state appeared to be favoured by increase in radius (or decrease in ionisation potential) of the metal and high pK value of the ligand" (Table 2); 2N1N, however, is an exception.

2N1N formed a number of stable complexes with alkali metal hydroxide in abs. ethanol or acetone of the type ML_nHL , where $n = 1$ or 2 , and $M = \text{Li-Cs}$. Picolinic acid formed a lesser number of stable complexes with K-, Rb- and Cs-hydroxide; and 2H3NA formed still lesser number of complexes than 2N1N or PicA, with Rb- and Cs-hydroxides.

1-Nitroso-2-naphthol do not form neutral complexes with LiOH and NaOH, whereas 2N1N with a lower pK value, formed neutral complexes of the type $MLHL$ with these two hydroxides. Again neutral complexes of $ML.2HL$ type, where $M = \text{Cs}$, were formed with 2N1N but not with 1N2N. So the position of the nitroso group in the ligand has a say in the ability of the ligand to form alkali metal complexes. Nitroso group in position 2 facilitates the formation of more complexes. It is observed that though pK value of the ligand is a dominant factor in the formation of alkali metal complexes, in some cases other factors predominate. One of the factors may be the chelating ability of the ligand and their donor properties towards the metal ion. Thus in the Table 2, the position of 2N1N between 1N2N and ONP do not seem to be anomalous.

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